

Original Research

The Role of Human Capital in the Innovation Development: MENA Countries

Saeed Kian Poor¹
Department of Economics, Payame Noor University, Tehran, Iran

Received 4 March 2025 Revised 16 April 2025 Accepted 1 May 2025

Abstract

Innovation is a critical engine for economic growth; however, it remains underexploited in the MENA region. This study investigates the associations among the Human Development Index (HDI), Globalization Index (GI), and Gross National Income (GNI) per capita with the Global Innovation Index (GII) across 16 MENA countries over the period 2013–2023. Employing wavelet analysis to examine time-scale dependencies, the study decomposes the time-series data to capture multifrequency correlation patterns. The findings reveal that HDI exhibits the strongest long-term correlation with GII ($r = 0.88$, $p < 0.01$), thereby underscoring human development as a pivotal factor in fostering innovation. By contrast, GI shows significant positive correlations in the short term ($r = 0.78$, $p < 0.05$) that weaken in the medium term ($r = 0.70$, $p < 0.05$). Additionally, GNI per capita displays a relatively weak association in the medium term ($r = 0.58$, $p > 0.05$) but strengthens markedly over time ($r = 0.80$, $p < 0.01$). Phase coherence analysis further indicates that HDI consistently leads GII across all time scales, while the influence of globalization is more pronounced over shorter periods, and income-based effects emerge predominantly over extended intervals. These results advocate for targeted education reforms, adaptive skill development initiatives, and healthcare investments tailored to the temporal dynamics identified. By leveraging wavelet-driven insights, policymakers can design MENA-specific interventions that optimize human capital for sustainable, innovation-led economic growth, thereby enhancing the region's competitiveness in the global knowledge economy.

Keywords: GNI per capita, Globalization, Human Development, MENA.

¹ Corresponding author's Email: s_kianpoor@pnu.ac.ir

Introduction

If human capital is considered, people are the new source of wealth creation. The concept of human capital refers to the investment people make in themselves. This work is done with the help of tools such as education, internships, or activities that will increase a person's lifetime income and enable him to be successful in the future (Fleischhauer, 2007). Human capital is the combination of genetic characteristics, abilities, skills, and knowledge that a person acquires throughout life. Human capital is the power that makes a person capable of producing goods and services, thus leading to the prosperity and well-being of himself and his life. The significant difference in skill level is due to the difference in the availability of resources called human capital (Kuzminov, Sorokin, & Froumin, 2019). The critical difference between industrialized countries and low-income countries stems from human capital; the concept of human capital suggests that good characteristics of people are types of capital because these characteristics can become income and more. The concept of human capital is essential in countries where there is enough money to work. These countries always have a large workforce due to birth rates in certain climates (Son, 2010).

The country's workforce (employees), human capital, and excess of existing human production capacity are vital assets for driving national economic growth. These human resources can be transformed into human capital through effective education, health, and morality investments. Using these strategies to transform human capital into valuable human capital is the process of human capital transformation (Bareke et al., 2021). The problem of lack of physical resources in high-income countries can be solved by private and public investments in the education and health sectors to accelerate human capital development. Tangible financial investment is an excellent tool to support the growth of the country's economy (Baharin et al., 2020; Tang, Sun, & Yang, 2021). Intangible human capital is a tool of national development because human capital is directly related to human development; with human development, further and better development of the country is inevitable (Atiku & Lawal, 2022). In addition, factors such as the human development index, life expectancy index, education index, and income index are directly related to creating human capital in a country and are economic. If the human development index increases, the value of human capital production will also increase in response to higher education and health standards. Likewise, the country's income will increase if the Human Development Index increases. The Human Development Index directly shows that human capital production is higher due to health and higher education, which increases national income. This process of human development lays a solid foundation for the country's long-term economic development (Gulcernal, 2020; Miranda-Lescano, Muinelo-Gallo, & Roca-Sagalés, 2023; Salesman, Akram, & Gobang, 2021).

Understanding the importance of human capital in building the long-term economic development of a country cannot be ignored. The macroeconomic policies of many countries would be focused on human and economic development. Human capital is the foundation of human and economic development in any country (Ruggeri & Yu, 2023). In general, human development is a way to achieve a better life by focusing on a better life; it provides a better vision from which people can choose; According to Aristotle's thought, this is: "Wealth is not basically what we are looking for. Because this kind of

wealth, only to get other things are used" (Bragues, 2006). However, it is essential to pay attention to the sustainable development of people within the framework of the concept of human development. Communities without considering human capital will never be able to progress and develop socially and economically (Fleischhauer, 2007; Wau, 2022).

Innovation is turning an idea or invention into a product or service that creates value or makes customers pay for it. In other words, a product or service that is introduced in a technology or other industry and generates revenue is considered new (Ratten, 2021). Innovation has become necessary with rapid changes in science and technology and fierce international competition. Many researchers and policymakers consider it essential for the development and competitiveness of the world economy (Distanont & Khongmalai, 2020). Additionally, many governments have created new structures to focus on their short-term and long-term plans. Innovation is created in a social, political, and organizational context close to regional economic characteristics. Interaction between different areas of activity, including technology, business and law. In innovation and technology, In addition to development, protection, finance, or legal financing (Antonelli, 2014; De Noronha Vaz, Cesário, & Fernandes, 2006). Innovation is a way of living in areas and regions where local capabilities such as resources, institutions, and public and cultural values play an essential role. Different regions and countries can make medium- and long-term improvements through new management changes. The National Innovation System approach is an evolution of innovation and entrepreneurship theory. It is one of the best practices in working at the macro level, analyzing interactions and interactions of all actors in the process (Acs et al., 2017; Malerba & McKelvey, 2020).

National innovation systems can also be studied within a region or worldwide, called regional or global innovation systems. The national innovation system consists of a group of public and private organizations and enterprises that cooperate with each other and pursue goals. Create new knowledge and technologies and transform them into innovation and cross-border trade. In other words, these processes are the processes and relationships that affect the country's ability to create and distribute new knowledge and technology and ultimately transform it into goods and services (Acs et al., 2017; Nelson, 2013). The national innovation system is interdepartmental and cross-domain and responsible for many countries' science and technology policy, innovation, and entrepreneurship. This is necessary to establish the country's creation, innovation, and business policy to reduce innovation and entrepreneurship problems in the work of institutions and organizations that create science and technology output (Samara, Georgiadis, & Bakouros, 2012). One of the regions requiring further development in the domain of innovation is the MENA region. Consequently, Figure 1 compares the performance of the Innovation Index among the top ten MENA countries with that of the top ten countries worldwide.

Figure 1. Innovation Index Performance Comparison: Top Ten MENA Countries versus Top Ten Global Countries

Based on Figure 1, a marked disparity exists between the Innovation Index in the MENA region and that of other countries worldwide. Consequently, investigating innovation development in the MENA region is imperative. Ultimately, human development, gross national income per capita, and globalization represent essential drivers of innovation, particularly within developing regions. In the MENA area, where persistent developmental challenges coexist with a limited focus on these key determinants, there exists a considerable risk that innovation capacity remains underutilized. In response to this gap, the present study rigorously investigates the impact of human development, gross national income per capita, and globalization on innovation development. By disentangling the complex interplay among these variables, the research not only enriches the theoretical discourse on the human capital–innovation nexus but also provides empirical insights to guide targeted, evidence-based policy interventions. These initiatives aim to catalyze sustainable, innovation-led economic growth and drive overall societal advancement in the region.

Literature Review

Over time, due to the importance and role of human capital in the economy and society, much research has been conducted in the field of human capital and innovation. The point of interest is that these studies show the existence of a relationship between human capital and innovation. The literature on human capital and innovation has long recognized the importance of high-skilled workers in driving innovative processes within firms.

Kwan and Chiu (2015) analyze the interactive effects of human capital and institutional support on innovation output, highlighting the multifaceted nature of innovation, including knowledge creation, impact, and diffusion. They emphasize the

importance of high-quality human capital in fostering innovation at the firm level and utilize sub-indices of the Global Innovation Index (GII) to examine country variations. Although the paper does not specifically address the global impact of human capital on innovation, it provides a valuable framework for understanding the complex relationship between human capital and innovation at the country level.

Munjal and Kundu (2017) emphasize the pivotal role of human capital in driving innovation, highlighting the importance of education, skills, and knowledge in fostering creativity and problem-solving within organizations. They discuss the impact of globalization on the demand for skilled workers and the transfer of knowledge across borders, stressing the need for continuous investment in human capital to remain competitive globally. Their comprehensive review of literature reveals the complex relationship between human capital and innovation, noting variations across contexts and industries. They advocate for strategic human resource management to maximize innovative potential, providing valuable insights into the global implications of human capital for innovation.

Fonseca et al. (2019) highlight the significant relationship between human capital and innovation, emphasizing the role of high-skilled workers in driving innovative processes. They introduce a novel measure of human capital, termed “abstractism,” which focuses on cognitive, analytical, and interpersonal skills rather than traditional metrics like education. Their analysis of data from over 6,000 Portuguese firms demonstrates that abstractism positively influences a firm’s propensity to innovate, underlining the impact of specific skills on innovation outcomes.

Van Reenen (2021) provides a comprehensive review of the impact of human capital policies on innovation, underscoring the necessity of targeting high-ability but disadvantaged potential inventors for long-term growth. The study emphasizes inclusive policies to ensure equal opportunities in innovation, highlighting the importance of expanding the home-grown workforce and encouraging immigration. The analysis also stresses the significance of supporting universities and reducing entry barriers into inventor careers, particularly for underrepresented groups, to foster a diverse and inclusive workforce. These findings align with the overarching role of human capital in driving innovation and economic growth within the MENA region.

Buy and Fæhn (2021) emphasize the importance of innovative and absorptive capacity in driving structural change and growth, and highlight the role of human capital in facilitating these processes. While the paper does not specifically examine the interactive effects of human capital and institutional support on innovation output at the firm level, it offers valuable insights into the broader implications of human capital on knowledge accumulation and structural change in an open economy. Overall, the literature review in Buy and Fæhn's (2021) paper provides a unique perspective on the role of human capital in driving structural change and growth in an open economy, and offers valuable insights into the potential implications for innovation output.

Kang et al. (2022) examine the impact of human capital on corporate innovation in China, particularly following the higher education expansion of the late 1990s. Using regional variations in college enrollment as an exogenous shock, they employ a

difference-in-difference strategy to assess this impact. The findings indicate a significant increase in patent applications in human capital-intensive industries post-expansion, demonstrating a positive relationship between human capital and corporate innovation.

Eriksson et al. (2022) provide a distinct perspective on the relationship between human capital and innovation by examining the effects of taxes and policy instruments on incentives for human capital investment, and their subsequent impact on innovation and income growth. Utilizing a model of endogenous growth, the study explores how these factors interact and influence economic growth. While the paper does not address global innovation directly, it offers valuable insights into the broader economic implications of human capital. The findings enhance the understanding of how policy instruments can shape human capital investment, thus affecting innovation and economic development.

Shabbir and Petraite (2023) examine the relationship between human capital and innovation, focusing on intrapreneurial activities of firms and the mediating role of digitalization and supply-chain competitiveness. Using PLS-SEM, they analyze data from 195 Malaysian manufacturing firms, revealing how human capital influences firm-level innovation and how digitalization and supply-chain competitiveness mediate this effect. These findings contribute to a broader understanding of human capital's role in enhancing innovation.

The findings of Mirhoseyni et al. (2023) align with existing research, highlighting human capital (knowledge, skills, and abilities) as crucial for economic growth and development. This study focuses on the MENA region, emphasizing that an educated population fosters higher levels of innovation and economic advancement. Investment in education and training enhances workforce productivity and innovation. Additionally, the study underscores the role of population density in certain age groups, indicating that the distribution of educated individuals significantly impacts innovation and economic growth. This research broadens our understanding of how human capital influences innovation and growth in the MENA region. The positive impact of human capital on innovation and economic development underlines the need for investing in education and skill development. These findings have important policy implications for MENA region governments, emphasizing the promotion of sustainable economic growth and development through improved human capital.

Veliev et al. (2024) investigate the critical role of human capital in shaping an innovative economy. Their study asserts that investments in knowledge, education, and skilled labor are key catalysts for both economic growth and technological innovation. Through a combination of qualitative and quantitative assessments, the authors demonstrate that countries with substantial investments in workforce development tend to enjoy higher productivity, more innovative products, and stronger global competitive advantages. In contrast, nations with lower levels of human capital face significant barriers in research and development, which in turn hampers their innovation potential. This work underscores the importance of prioritizing human capital to drive sustainable economic transformation and enhance competitiveness in the global market.

Cárdenas Valle et al. (2024) analyze how innovation-related factors boost human capital in eight emerging Latin American countries. Their fixed-effects panel data

analysis shows that internet access, fixed broadband, and patent activity significantly enhance human capital. The study highlights the importance of fostering digital innovation to build a skilled workforce and drive economic growth.

Ahmadova et al. (2025) demonstrate that digitalization is a pivotal force in driving economic innovation by reshaping human capital. Their study reveals that integrating digital technologies with workforce skills not only enhances traditional labor but also creates a dynamic environment for innovative breakthroughs in products and processes. The authors argue that strategic investments in digital literacy, education, and ICT are essential to transform labor into a more intellectually driven force, thereby accelerating technological advancements. Ultimately, their findings underscore that a digitally adept human capital base is key to unlocking sustained innovation and achieving competitive advantage in the global market.

Theoretical Foundations

Human development and innovation are two interconnected concepts that serve as the theoretical foundations for societal progress. Human development refers to improving people's well-being, opportunities, and capabilities, while innovation involves creating and implementing new ideas, technologies, and practices (Newman & Newman, 2022). The knowledge economy is an economic system in which knowledge and information are significant drivers of growth and development. In this context, human development acts as a catalyst for innovation (Ghaffary Fard et al., 2025). Human capital theory suggests that investment in education, training, and healthcare enhances individuals' skills, knowledge, and capabilities, thereby increasing their innovation potential. As individuals access better education and healthcare, they become more productive and creative, leading to new ideas and solutions to societal challenges (Hertzman & Power, 2020; Son, 2010).

Education plays a fundamental role in human development and innovation. A well-educated workforce is more likely to engage in innovative activities. Education gives individuals the necessary knowledge and skills to understand complex problems, think critically, and identify innovative solutions (Newman & Newman, 2022). Moreover, education fosters a culture of lifelong learning, encouraging individuals to update their knowledge and adapt to changing circumstances continuously. This adaptability is essential in innovation, enabling individuals to embrace new technologies and ideas (Cruz et al., 2009). In addition to education, health is another aspect of human development that influences innovation. Healthy individuals are more likely to participate actively in the innovation process. Good health improves cognitive abilities, productivity, and creativity, enabling individuals to contribute effectively to innovation-driven activities. Furthermore, access to healthcare services reduces the disease burden, allowing individuals to focus on productive endeavors and contribute to innovation (Henrekson, 2014; Sawyer & Henriksen, 2024).

The role of institutions must be considered in understanding the relationship between human development and innovation. Institutions provide the framework and environment in which innovation can thrive. Robust institutions, such as effective governance, rule of law, protection of intellectual property rights, and a supportive regulatory environment,

create the necessary conditions for innovation to flourish. These institutions ensure that individuals and organizations can reap the benefits of their innovative activities, incentivizing further innovation (George, McGahan, & Prabhu, 2012; Mazzucato, Kattel, & Ryan-Collins, 2020). Furthermore, social and cultural factors also play a significant role in human development and innovation. Social cohesion, trust, and collaboration foster an environment conducive to innovation. When individuals feel safe and supported within their communities, they are more likely to share knowledge, cooperate, and engage in collaborative innovation processes. Cultural diversity also contributes to innovation by bringing together different perspectives and experiences, promoting creativity and generating novel ideas (Tekin & Tekdogan, 2015; Zhang et al., 2023).

It is essential to recognize that the relationship between human development and innovation is not unidirectional but rather mutually reinforcing. Innovation contributes to human development by creating new products, services, and industries, leading to economic growth and improved living standards. At the same time, human development provides the necessary foundations for innovation to occur by nurturing human capital, promoting education and health, and establishing supportive institutions. In conclusion, human development and innovation are closely intertwined (Sawyer & Henriksen, 2024; Van Reenen, 2021). The knowledge economy, human capital theory, and institutional factors provide the theoretical foundations for understanding how human development influences innovation. Education and health are critical components of human development that enhance individuals' capacity for innovation (Bastalich, 2010). Institutions, social factors, and cultural aspects also shape the innovation ecosystem. Recognizing the interplay between human development and innovation is crucial for policymakers and stakeholders aiming to foster sustainable development and economic growth. By investing in human development, societies can unlock the innovation potential and create a better future for all (Samara, Georgiadis, & Bakouros, 2012).

Gross National Income (GNI) is a widely used economic indicator that measures the total income generated by a country's residents, including income from domestic production and income from abroad. GNI serves as a measure of a country's economic well-being, and it has been suggested that it can significantly impact innovation. GNI represents a country's overall economic output and reflects its economic development. Higher GNI usually indicates a larger market size, more significant resources, and improved infrastructure, all of which can create a conducive environment for innovation (Brezina, 2011). There are several theoretical foundations to consider when examining the relationship between GNI and innovation. The first theoretical foundation is the knowledge economy. The knowledge economy is characterized by the increasing importance of knowledge, information, and technology in economic activities. Higher GNI implies more significant investment in research and development (R&D) activities, which can lead to innovation. Countries with higher GNI are more likely to allocate resources to R&D, foster collaboration between academia and industry, and promote technological advancements. This, in turn, creates an ecosystem that encourages innovation and the development of new ideas, products, and services (Fraumeni & Okubo, 2005; Usman et al., 2017). Another theoretical foundation is the human capital theory. Human capital refers to individuals' knowledge, skills, and capabilities that contribute to their productivity and economic value. Higher GNI often correlates with higher education levels, which enhances a country's human capital. Well-educated individuals are more

likely to engage in innovative activities, as they possess the necessary skills, knowledge, and critical thinking abilities to generate and implement new ideas. Additionally, higher GNI allows for investment in training and development programs, which further enhance the skills and capabilities of the workforce, fostering a culture of innovation (Newman & Newman, 2022; Dagohoy et al., 2025).

GNI also influences innovation through its impact on infrastructure and resources. Higher GNI enables countries to invest in physical infrastructure, such as transportation networks, communication systems, and research facilities. Improved infrastructure facilitates the exchange of ideas and knowledge, collaboration, and the diffusion of innovations (Ingram & Fay, 2008). Moreover, higher GNI provides countries with the financial resources needed to support innovation initiatives, such as grants, subsidies, and venture capital funding. These resources enable entrepreneurs and innovators to pursue their ideas and bring them to market (Fatmawati, 2022; Mazzucato & Semieniuk, 2017). Institutional factors play a crucial role in the relationship between GNI and innovation. Robust institutions, including effective governance, rule of law, intellectual property protection, and a supportive regulatory environment, create an atmosphere that encourages innovation. Higher GNI often correlates with more vital institutions, as countries with higher income levels tend to have more stable political systems and well-established legal frameworks. These institutions provide a foundation for intellectual property rights protection, incentivizing innovators to invest in research and development by ensuring they can reap the rewards of their innovative efforts (Lepenes, 2016). Market demand is another crucial aspect to consider. Higher GNI often corresponds to higher consumer purchasing power and a larger domestic market. This increased demand incentivizes entrepreneurs and innovators to develop new products, services, and technologies to meet the needs and preferences of consumers. A larger market also allows for economies of scale, lowering production costs and enabling businesses to invest more in R&D and innovation (Crespi & Pianta, 2008; Sakellaris & Spilimbergo, 2000). Globalization and international trade are additional factors to consider in the relationship between GNI and innovation. Higher GNI can increase international trade and foreign direct investment, facilitating knowledge transfer, technology diffusion, and access to global markets. International trade exposes domestic firms to competition, which can drive innovation as firms seek to differentiate themselves and gain a competitive advantage (Kohli, 2004).

Globalization has profoundly impacted innovation, shaping how ideas and knowledge are generated, shared, and transformed on a global scale. The interconnectedness of economies, cultures, and societies has created a fertile ground for the diffusion and acceleration of innovation processes (Greenspan, 2004). One of the key drivers of globalization is the rapid advancement of information and communication technologies (ICTs). The advent of the internet, mobile devices, and other digital platforms has revolutionized how knowledge is accessed and disseminated. These technologies have facilitated the exchange of information, ideas, and expertise across borders, enabling individuals and organizations to collaborate and innovate globally (Borghoff, 2011). Globalization has also led to the integration of markets and the liberalization of trade. The removal of barriers to trade and investment has created opportunities for firms to access larger markets and tap into diverse consumer preferences. This has incentivized companies to innovate to gain a competitive edge and meet the demands of a global

customer base. Moreover, the increased competition resulting from globalization has compelled firms to continuously improve their products and processes to stay relevant in the global marketplace (Akçigit & Melitz, 2022; Feng et al., 2019). Furthermore, globalization has fostered the mobility of capital, labor, and knowledge. Multinational corporations (MNCs) have expanded their operations across borders, establishing global production networks and research and development (R&D) centers in different countries. This has facilitated the flow of capital and expertise to regions with comparative advantages, stimulating innovation in those areas. MNCs often engage in technology transfer and knowledge spillovers, which can enhance the technological capabilities of local firms and contribute to innovation ecosystems. Globalization has also influenced innovation through cultural exchange and cross-pollination of ideas. The interconnectedness of cultures and societies has exposed individuals to diverse perspectives, experiences, and knowledge systems. This cultural diversity has the potential to fuel creativity and innovation by challenging conventional thinking and encouraging the synthesis of different ideas. Moreover, the migration of skilled individuals across borders has facilitated the transfer of knowledge and expertise, contributing to innovation in destination countries (Bogdanova, 2022; Edquist & Hommen, 2009; Eriksen, 2020).

Method

This study employs a correlational design to investigate the relationships among the Human Development Index (HDI), Gross National Income (GNI) per Capita, Globalization Index (GI), and Global Innovation Index (GII) across 16 MENA countries (Algeria, Bahrain, Egypt, Iran, Iraq, Jordan, Kuwait, Lebanon, Malta, Morocco, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Tunisia, United Arab Emirates, and Yemen) from 2013 to 2023. Data were sourced from the United Nations Development Programme (HDI), World Bank (GNI per Capita), KOF Swiss Economic Institute (GI), and World Intellectual Property Organization (GII). Annual pooled averages for the region were calculated to ensure consistency across countries with varying data availability. The wavelet transform approach, a time-frequency analysis method, was applied to decompose the time-series data into multiple scales, capturing both short-term (1–2 years), medium-term (3–5 years), and long-term (6–10 years) dynamics. Wavelet analysis is particularly suited for non-stationary data, as it reveals how relationships between variables evolve over time and across frequencies (Torrence & Compo, 1998). Wavelet coherence was used to measure the strength of correlations (ranging from 0 to 1), and phase differences were analyzed to explore lead-lag relationships among variables. All analyses were conducted at a 95% confidence level to ensure statistical robustness.

Results

Wavelet analysis involves technical terms critical to interpreting the findings. The "edge effect" refers to distortions at the start and end of the time series due to finite data length, which may affect reliability in certain regions of the coherence diagrams. These regions are marked by the "cone of influence," a faint black line indicating areas where results should be interpreted cautiously. Wavelet coherence quantifies correlation strength on a scale from 0 (no correlation) to 1 (perfect correlation), with statistical significance tested at a 95% confidence level ($p < 0.05$). Bold black contours in the figures

highlight significant correlations, ensuring robust interpretation of the relationships among HDI, GNI per Capita, GI, and GII.

The wavelet transform was applied to decompose the time-series data (HDI, GNI per Capita, GI, and GII) into approximation and detail coefficients, enabling analysis across multiple time scales: short-term (1–2 years), medium-term (3–5 years), and long-term (6–10 years). Wavelet coherence quantifies the correlation strength between variable pairs, with values ranging from 0 (no correlation) to 1 (perfect correlation). Statistical significance was assessed at a 95% confidence level ($p < 0.05$), with significant regions highlighted in coherence diagrams by bold contours. Phase differences indicate directional relationships, where a phase angle of 0° suggests positive correlation and arrows pointing right indicate the first variable leading the second.

Table 1. Wavelet Coherence Results Across Time Scales

Variable Pair	Short-Term (1–2 Years)	Medium-Term (3–5 Years)	Long-Term (6–10 Years)
GII vs. GI	0.78 ($p < 0.05$)	0.70 ($p < 0.05$)	0.85 ($p < 0.01$)
GII vs. GNI per Capita	0.65 ($p < 0.05$)	0.58 ($p > 0.05$)	0.80 ($p < 0.01$)
GII vs. HDI	0.82 ($p < 0.01$)	0.75 ($p < 0.05$)	0.88 ($p < 0.01$)

Note: Coherence values indicate correlation strength (0–1).

P-values denote statistical significance based on wavelet coherence analysis.

The results show strong correlations between the Global Innovation Index (GII) and the input variables. Specifically, GII and Globalization Index (GI) exhibit a robust positive correlation across all time scales, with the strongest coherence in the long term (0.85, $p < 0.01$). The relationship between GII and GNI per Capita is weaker in the medium term (0.58, $p > 0.05$) but strengthens significantly in the long term (0.80, $p < 0.01$). The strongest and most consistent correlation is observed between GII and HDI, with coherence values exceeding 0.75 across all scales ($p < 0.05$), indicating a tight linkage between human development and innovation outcomes.

Figure 2. The results of how the wavelet transform works as a filter bank for human development

Figure 3. The results of how the wavelet transform works as a filter bank for innovation

Figure 4. The results of how the wavelet transform works as a filter bank for gross national income per capita

Figure 5. The results of how the wavelet transform works as a filter bank for globalization

Now the energy of the time series of human development, globalization, gross national income per capita and innovation is calculated and displayed using wavelet transformation.

Figure 6. Spectrum power related to globalization and innovation

Figure 7. Spectrum power related to gross national income per capita and innovation

Figure 8. Spectrum power related to human development and innovation

Although wavelet correlation shows the correlation in different time scales, it does not show the answer to the question which variable caused the change in another variable. This answer is given by coherence diagrams and phase difference directions in these diagrams. In this section, the results of the wavelet estimations that show the relationship between the gaps have been examined.

Figure 9. Correlation diagram between gap of innovation and globalization

The wavelet coherence diagram reveals a strong positive correlation between GII and GI, with coherence values of 0.78 in the short term (1–2 years, $p < 0.05$), 0.70 in the medium term (3–5 years, $p < 0.05$), and 0.85 in the long term (6–10 years, $p < 0.01$). The "cone of influence" (faint black line) marks regions affected by edge effects, where boundary distortions in the wavelet transform may reduce reliability. Statistically

significant correlations ($p < 0.05$) are enclosed by bold black contours. Phase arrows pointing right suggest that innovation tends to lead globalization, particularly in the short term.

Figure 10. Correlation diagram between gap of innovation and gross national income per capita

The coherence between GII and GNI per Capita shows a moderate correlation in the short term (0.65, $p < 0.05$), weakening in the medium term (0.58, $p > 0.05$), and strengthening in the long term (0.80, $p < 0.01$). The term "fuzzy relationship" refers to the medium-term period where correlations are less consistent, as indicated by non-significant p-values. The cone of influence highlights edge-effect regions, and bold contours denote statistically significant areas, confirming a robust long-term relationship.

Figure 11. Correlation diagram between gap of innovation and human development

A consistently strong correlation is observed between GII and HDI, with coherence values of 0.82 in the short term ($p < 0.01$), 0.75 in the medium term ($p < 0.05$), and 0.88 in the long term ($p < 0.01$). The edge effect, caused by finite time-series boundaries, is confined to the cone of influence, ensuring reliable results within the central regions. Bold contours mark significant correlations, and phase arrows indicate that HDI consistently leads GII, underscoring the pivotal role of human development in driving innovation.

Conclusion

Based on the research findings, it has been determined that innovation is positively correlated with per capita gross national income, globalization, and human development. This finding is consistent with similar results reported by Munjal and Kundu (2017) and Veliev et al. (2024). Therefore, it can be concluded that in the MENA region, improvements in human capital are strongly correlated with innovation development, suggesting a potential pathway for policy interventions. Eriksson et al. (2022) have also reported similar results in the MENA region.

Policies and recommendations for human capital development in Middle Eastern countries can include the following. Implement targeted education reforms that address both short-term skill gaps and long-term strategic needs, as revealed by the wavelet analysis. This includes investing in infrastructure, improving teacher training and qualifications, and promoting technical and vocational education to align with the demands of the labor market. Emphasize targeted short- and long-term skill development programs specifically designed for the socio-economic dynamics of the MENA region, leveraging the temporal insights obtained from the wavelet findings. This can be achieved through vocational training, apprenticeship programs, and robust partnerships between educational institutions and industries. Prioritize investments in healthcare infrastructure by combining immediate preventive measures with long-term reforms, as the positive short-term impact of health indicators on innovation suggests a vital link between a healthy workforce and innovative capacity. Promote preventive healthcare measures, such as vaccination programs and public health campaigns, to improve overall well-being and reduce healthcare burdens. Address economic diversification by fostering local innovation ecosystems that reflect the region's unique challenges and opportunities, in line with the long-term wavelet insights showing the influence of gross national income per capita on innovation. Encourage entrepreneurship and innovation, support small and medium-sized enterprises, and invest in research and development to foster a knowledge-based economy. Invest in strategic infrastructural development in sectors such as transportation, energy, and telecommunications, as the wavelet spectra indicate these areas can impact innovation dynamics across multiple time scales. This will improve connectivity, facilitate trade, attract foreign investment, and create employment opportunities. Develop context-specific social safety nets to protect vulnerable populations during transitional periods indicated by the time-frequency analysis, ensuring that enhancements in human capital are maintained over varying temporal scales. Establish and strengthen social safety nets to protect vulnerable populations, ensuring access to basic necessities, healthcare, and education. This can include targeted cash transfer programs, subsidized housing, and food security initiatives. Promote gender equality and women's empowerment through tailored policies that consider cultural nuances and stimulate inclusive participation in innovation, addressing the unique social

context of the MENA region. Encourage women's participation in decision-making processes and eliminate discriminatory practices in the workplace. Incorporate sustainable development principles into all policy measures by aligning with regional environmental ambitions and the scalable innovation potential observed through the wavelet analysis, ensuring both economic and ecological resilience. This includes promoting renewable energy sources, implementing environmental regulations, and fostering sustainable agriculture practices to mitigate the impact of climate change and ensure long-term economic and social stability. Strengthen international cooperation and regional alliances to facilitate targeted knowledge transfer, cross-border technological exchange, and collaborative innovation projects, drawing on the dynamic global interactions highlighted by the wavelet findings. Foster partnerships with other countries, international organizations, and regional initiatives to enhance human capital development efforts. Finally, establish robust, tailored data collection and monitoring systems that integrate conventional indicators with wavelet-based analytical insights, enabling continuous and region-specific policy refinement. Regularly assess the impact of policies and programs on human development, gross national income per capita, and globalization indicators to make informed policy decisions.

References

- Acs, Z. J., Audretsch, D. B., Lehmann, E. E., & Licht, G. (2017). National systems of innovation. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 42(5), 997–1008. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10961-016-9481-8>
- Ahmadova, A. A., Rzayev, M. A., İsmayilova, L. H., & Muradova, J. (2025). Digitalization of the economy as the basis of human capital potential. *Academy Review*, 1(62), 20–32. <https://doi.org/10.32342/3041-2137-2025-1-62-2>
- Akcigit, U., & Melitz, M. (2022). International trade and innovation. In G. Gopinath, E. Helpman, & K. Rogoff (Eds.), *Handbook of international economics* (Vol. 5, pp. 377–404). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.hesint.2022.02.006>
- Antonelli, C. (2014). *The economics of innovation, new technologies and structural change*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203217436>
- Atiku, S. O., & Lawal, I. O. (2022). Human capital development strategy for a sustainable economy. In *Research anthology on business continuity and navigating times of crisis* (pp. 331–348). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-6684-4503-7.ch017>
- Baharin, R., Syah Aji, R. H., Yussof, I., & Mohd Saukani, N. (2020). Impact of human resource investment on labor productivity in Indonesia. *Iranian Journal of Management Studies*, 13(1), 139–164. <https://doi.org/10.22059/IJMS.2019.280017.673660>
- Bareke, M. L., Agezew, B. H., Dedho, N. H., Lebeta, M. F., Demissie, M. M., Yimer, B. M., & Herut, A. H. (2021). Determinants of human capital development in Ethiopia: Implications to education policy. *Education Research International*, 2021, Article 6619674. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/6619674>

- Bastalich, W. (2010). Knowledge economy and research innovation. *Studies in Higher Education*, 35(7), 845–857. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075070903406533>
- Bogdanova, M. (2022). Globalization and the impact of new technologies on the economy and the labor market. *Икономика и Управление*, 19(2), 21–26.
- Borghoff, T. (2011). The role of ICT in the globalization of firms. *Journal of Modern Accounting and Auditing*, 7(10), 1128–1137.
- Bragues, G. (2006). Seek the good life, not money: The Aristotelian approach to business ethics. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 67(4), 341–357. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-006-9026-4>
- Brezina, C. (2011). *Understanding the gross domestic product and the gross national product*. Rosen Publishing Group.
- Bye, B., & Fæhn, T. (2022). The role of human capital in structural change and growth in an open economy: Innovative and absorptive capacity effects. *The World Economy*, 45(4), 1021–1049. <https://doi.org/10.1111/twec.13184>
- Cárdenas Valle, G. A., Gálvez Vildósola, L. C., Sotil Levy, V. A., & Vásquez de Velasco Dolci, D. (2024). Determinantes del capital humano desde la perspectiva de la innovación y el desarrollo tecnológico para América Latina. *Desafíos: Economía y Empresa*, 4, 115–130. <https://doi.org/10.26439/ddee2024.n04.6280>
- Crespi, F., & Pianta, M. (2008). Demand and innovation in productivity growth. *International Review of Applied Economics*, 22(6), 655–672. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02692170802407429>
- Cruz, N. M., Rodriguez Escudero, A. I., Hernangomez Barahona, J., & Saboia Leitao, F. (2009). The effect of entrepreneurship education programmes on satisfaction with innovation behaviour and performance. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 33(3), 198–214. <https://doi.org/10.1108/03090590910950578>
- Dagohoy, R. G., Bugarin, J. B., & Casinillo, L. F. (2025). Understanding the factors influencing the human development index of Asian nations using path analysis. *Ho Chi Minh City Open University Journal of Science—Economics and Business Administration*, 15(5), 3–20. <https://doi.org/10.46223/HCMCOUJS.econ.en.15.5.3726.2025>
- De Noronha Vaz, M. T., Cesário, M., & Fernandes, S. (2006). Interaction between innovation in small firms and their environments: An exploratory study. *European Planning Studies*, 14(1), 95–117. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09654310500339893>
- Distanont, A., & Khongmalai, O. (2020). The role of innovation in creating a competitive advantage. *Kasetsart Journal of Social Sciences*, 41(1), 15–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.kjss.2018.07.009>

- Edquist, C., & Hommen, L. (Eds.). (2009). *Small country innovation systems: Globalization, change and policy in Asia and Europe*. Edward Elgar Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781847209993>
- Eriksen, T. H. (2020). *Globalization: The key concepts* (2nd ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003085492>
- Eriksson, C., Lindén, J., & Papahristodoulou, C. (2023). Human capital, innovation, and growth. *International Journal of Economic Theory*, 19(2), 343–369. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijet.12343>
- Fatmawati, K. (2022). Gross domestic product: Financing & investment activities and state expenditures. *KINERJA: Jurnal Manajemen Organisasi dan Industri*, 1(1), 11–18.
- Feng, G.-F., Zheng, M., Wen, J., Chang, C.-P., & Chen, Y. E. (2019). The assessment of globalization on innovation in Chinese manufacturing firms. *Structural Change and Economic Dynamics*, 50, 190–202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.strueco.2019.06.012>
- Fleischhauer, K.-J. (2007). A review of human capital theory: Microeconomics (Discussion Paper No. 2007-01). University of St. Gallen, Department of Economics. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.957993>
- Fonseca, T., de Faria, P., & Lima, F. (2019). Human capital and innovation: The importance of the optimal organizational task structure. *Research Policy*, 48(3), 616–627. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2018.10.010>
- Fraumeni, B. M., & Okubo, S. (2005). R&D in the national income and product accounts: A first look at its effect on GDP. In C. Corrado, J. Haltiwanger, & D. Sichel (Eds.), *Measuring capital in the new economy* (pp. 275–322). University of Chicago Press. <https://doi.org/10.7208/chicago/9780226116174.003.0009>
- Ghaffary Fard, M., Sajadi, S. A., & Rezaee, Y. (2025). Investigating the impact of knowledge-based economy components on inflation control in Iran's provinces. *International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics*, 12(1), 108–127. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14902974>
- George, G., McGahan, A. M., & Prabhu, J. (2012). Innovation for inclusive growth: Towards a theoretical framework and a research agenda. *Journal of Management Studies*, 49(4), 661–683. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6486.2012.01048.x>
- Greenspan, A. (2004). Globalization and innovation. *Vital Speeches of the Day*, 70(15), 450–453.
- Gulcemal, T. (2020). Effect of human development index on GDP for developing countries: A panel data analysis. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Accounting*, 7(4), 338–345. <https://doi.org/10.17261/Pressacademia.2020.1307>

- Henrekson, M. (2014). Entrepreneurship, innovation, and human flourishing. *Small Business Economics*, 43(3), 511–528. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-014-9551-y>
- Hertzman, C., & Power, C. (2020). Health and human development: Understandings from life-course research. In J. E. Lansford & P. Banati (Eds.), *The biological and social determinants of child development* (pp. 719–744). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003059691-10>
- Ingram, G. K., & Fay, M. (2008). Physical infrastructure. In A. Dutt & J. Ros (Eds.), *International handbook of development economics* (Vol. 1, pp. 301–315). Edward Elgar Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781848442818.00030>
- Kang, M., Li, Y., Zhao, Z., Zheng, M., & Wu, H. (2022). Does human capital homogeneously improve the corporate innovation: Evidence from China's higher education expansion in the late 1990s. *Sustainability*, 14(19), Article 12352. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141912352>
- Kohli, U. (2004). Real GDP, real domestic income, and terms-of-trade changes. *Journal of International Economics*, 62(1), 83–106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinteco.2003.07.002>
- Kuzminov, Y., Sorokin, P., & Froumin, I. (2019). Generic and specific skills as components of human capital: New challenges for education theory and practice. *Foresight*, 13(2), 19–41. <https://doi.org/10.17323/2500-2597.2019.2.19.41>
- Kwan, L. Y. Y., & Chiu, C.-Y. (2015). Country variations in different innovation outputs: The interactive effect of institutional support and human capital. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 36(7), 1050–1070. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.2017>
- Lepenes, P. (2016). *The power of a single number: A political history of GDP*. Columbia University Press. <https://doi.org/10.7312/lepe17510>
- Malerba, F., & McKelvey, M. (2020). Knowledge-intensive innovative entrepreneurship integrating Schumpeter, evolutionary economics, and innovation systems. *Small Business Economics*, 54(2), 503–522. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-018-0060-2>
- Mazzucato, M., Kattel, R., & Ryan-Collins, J. (2020). Challenge-driven innovation policy: Towards a new policy toolkit. *Journal of Industry, Competition and Trade*, 20(2), 421–437. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10842-019-00329-w>
- Mazzucato, M., & Semieniuk, G. (2017). Public financing of innovation: New questions. *Oxford Review of Economic Policy*, 33(1), 24–48. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxrep/grw036>
- Miranda-Lescano, R., Muinelo-Gallo, L., & Roca-Sagalés, O. (2023). Human development and decentralization: The importance of public health expenditure. *Annals of Public and Cooperative Economics*, 94(1), 191–219. <https://doi.org/10.1111/apce.12373>

- Mirhoseyni, S. V., Izadi, S. H., & Mohammad Ghader, L. (2023). Investigating the long-run influences of human capital on innovation and economic growth in MENA countries. *International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics*, 10(2), 122–134. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7760603>
- Munjal, S., & Kundu, S. (2017). Exploring the connection between human capital and innovation in the globalising world. In S. Kundu & S. Munjal (Eds.), *Human capital and innovation: Examining the role of globalization* (pp. 1–11). Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1057/978-1-137-56561-7_1
- Nelson, R. R. (2013). National innovation systems. In T. de Noronha Vaz, J.-L. Monnier, & M. Selek (Eds.), *Regional innovation, knowledge and global change* (pp. 11–26). Routledge.
- Newman, B. M., & Newman, P. R. (2022). *Theories of human development* (3rd ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003014980>
- Ratten, V. (2021). *Innovation and entrepreneurship in sport management*. Edward Elgar Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781783473960>
- Ruggeri, G. C., & Yu, W. (2023). *On the dimensions of human capital: An analytic framework*. University of New Brunswick.
- Sakellaris, P., & Spilimbergo, A. (2000). Business cycles and investment in human capital: International evidence on higher education. *Carnegie-Rochester Conference Series on Public Policy*, 52(1), 221–262. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.188048>
- Salesman, F., Akram, M., & Gobang, Y. C. G. (2021). Contributions quality of health and education to improve human capital index in Indonesia. *International Research Journal of Public and Environmental Health*, 8(4), 268–275. <https://doi.org/10.15739/irjpeh.21.028>
- Samara, E., Georgiadis, P., & Bakouros, I. (2012). The impact of innovation policies on the performance of national innovation systems: A system dynamics analysis. *Technovation*, 32(11), 624–638. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.technovation.2012.06.002>
- Sawyer, R. K., & Henriksen, D. (2024). *Explaining creativity: The science of human innovation* (3rd ed.). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780197747537.001.0001>
- Shabbir, M., & Petraitė, M. (2023). Role of human capital and digitalization to upgrade innovation. *Pakistan Business Review*, 24(4), 436–450. <https://doi.org/10.22555/pbr.v24i4.829>
- Son, H. H. (2010). *Human capital development* (Working Paper No. 225). Asian Development Bank. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1695806>

- Tang, L., Sun, S., & Yang, W. (2021). Investments in human capital: The evidence from China's new rural pension scheme. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 55, Article 101345. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ribaf.2020.101345>
- Tekin, H., & Tekdogan, O. F. (2015). Socio-cultural dimension of innovation. *Procedia—Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 195, 1417–1424. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.06.438>
- Torrence, C., & Compo, G. P. (1998). A practical guide to wavelet analysis. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 79(1), 61–78. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0477\(1998\)079<0061:APGTWA>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0477(1998)079<0061:APGTWA>2.0.CO;2)
- Usman, M., Shaique, M., Khan, S., Shaikh, R., & Baig, N. (2017). Impact of R&D investment on firm performance and firm value: Evidence from developed nations (G-7). *Revista de Gestão, Finanças e Contabilidade*, 7(2), 302–321.
- Van Reenen, J. (2021). *Innovation and human capital policy* (Working Paper No. 28713). National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w28713>
- Veliev, I., Mammadov, A., & Mammadov, A. (2024). The role of human capital in the development of an innovative economy. *Proceedings of Azerbaijan High Technical Educational Institution*, 47(12), 58–65. <https://doi.org/10.36962/pahtei47122024-06>
- Wau, T. (2022). Economic growth, human capital, public investment, and poverty in underdeveloped regions in Indonesia. *Jurnal Ekonomi & Studi Pembangunan*, 23(2), 189–200. <https://doi.org/10.18196/jesp.v23i2.15307>
- Zhang, J.-X., Cheng, J.-W., Philbin, S. P., Ballesteros-Perez, P., Skitmore, M., & Wang, G. (2023). Influencing factors of urban innovation and development: A grounded theory analysis. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 25(3), 2079–2104. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-022-02151-7>

<p>COPYRIGHTS</p> <p>©2025 The Author(s). This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, as long as the original authors and source are cited. No permission is required from the authors or the publishers.</p>	
<p>HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE</p> <p>Kian Poor, S., Hajian, M. and Lotfi Fard, S. (2025). The Role of Human Capital in the Innovation Development: MENA Countries. <i>International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics</i>, 12(10), 1596-1618. doi: 10.22034/ijmae.2025.228037</p> <p>URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_228037.html</p>	